

Studies in Thiazolo Quinoxaline. Part II

Simran Singh* and Chanan Singh

Condensations of N-N' diaryl thioureas with 2:3-dichloro quinoxalines furnished 2-arylimino-3-aryl-2:3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxalines. These products underwent hydrolysis with ethanolic potassium hydroxide when 2-keto-3-aryl-2:3-dihydro thiazolo(4,5-b) quinoxalines were obtained.

In 2:3-dichloro quinoxalines, the α -carbon atoms bound to chlorine and nitrogen (through double bonds) are highly electrophilic and react quite smoothly with nucleophilic centres in thioureas viz., nitrogen and sulphur¹⁻⁴. Unlike N-aryl thioureas⁵ only single products are obtained because of the symmetric nature of thioureas. The formation of the imidazole derivative (IV) is ruled out as on hydrolysis these products furnish 2-keto-3-aryl-2:3-dihydro thiazolo (4, 5-b) quinoxaline (V).

* Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana.

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TABLE

2 : 3-Disubstituted thiazolo (4,5-b)quinoxalines (III)

S.No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C*	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analytical Results**	
							Found %	Required%
1	H	H	H ₆ H ₅	200	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S	N : 16.21	15.81
2	H	NO ₂	„	203	78	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ SO ₂	N : 17.11	17.54
3	NO ₂	NO ₂	„	192	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₆ SO ₄	N : 18.41	18.92
4	Cl	H	„	195	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ S	N : 14.01	14.43
5	CH ₃	H	„	204	70	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	N : 15.26	15.21
6	H	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	190	80	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	C : 71.70 H : 4.61 N : 14.59	72.25 4.71 14.65
7	H	NO ₂	„	185	85	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO ₂	N : 16.30	16.39
8	NO ₂	NO ₂	„	240	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ SO ₄	N : 17.39	17.79
9	CH ₃	H	„	220	70	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	N : 13.71	14.14
10	CH ₃	H	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	214	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	N : 14.47	14.14
11	Cl	H	„	208	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ S	N : 13.77	13.46
12	H	NO ₂	„	205	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO ₂	N : 16.20	16.39
13	H	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	197	70	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ SO ₂	N : 13.58	13.52
14	CH ₃	H	„	186	78	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ SO ₂	N : 13.12	13.08
15	NO ₂	NO ₂	„	195	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ SO ₆	N : 16.32	16.66
16	H	NO ₂	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	190	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO ₂	N : 16.35	16.39
17	NO ₂	NO ₂	„	197	62	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₆ SO ₄	N : 17.60	17.79
18	Cl	H	„	265	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ S	N : 13.50	13.46
19	H	NO ₂	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	208	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₆ SO ₂	N : 14.65	14.95
20	Cl	H	„	220	72	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ N ₄ S	N : 11.92 S : 6.60	12.25 6.85
21	Cl	H	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl	150	63	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₃ N ₄ S	N : 11.83	12.25
22	H	NO ₂	„	215	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₅ SO ₂	N : 14.63	14.95
23	H	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Br	240	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₄ S	N : 11.18	10.93
24	H	NO ₂	„	213	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₅ SO ₂	N : 12.60	12.56
25	CH ₃	H	„	225	80	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄ S	N : 10.13 S : 5.85	10.64 6.08
26	H	NO ₂	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	220	65	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO ₄	N : 14.95	15.21

* All these compounds were crystallised from acetic acid.

** Analytical results are by M/s B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar of Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Arylimino-3-aryl-2:3-dihydro thiazolo (4, 5-b) quinoxaline. General Procedure : Equivalent amounts of 2:3-dichloro quinoxalines and N-N'-diaryl thioureas⁶ were refluxed in ethanol. The solids that started separating after about half an hour on cooling were filtered and washed with aqueous sodium carbonate solution to free them from any traces of hydrochloric acid and finally with water. The products were crystallised from acetic acid. The ethanolic filtrates were concentrated and the small amount of the products obtained after crystallisation were found to be identical with the above products. In the I.R. spectra—C' = N absorbed at 1600–1625 cm^{-1} and the peak 1570–1580 cm^{-1} , has been referred to a combination of C, N and S⁷. The details of the products are given in the table.

Treatment of 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-thiazolo (4, 5-b) quinoxaline with ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution : 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-2:3-dihydro thiazolo (4, 5-b) quinoxaline (II, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$, $R_3 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) (2 g) was refluxed with ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution (5%, 30 ml) for one and a half hours. It was steam distilled and steam distillate gave azo red dye test for aniline and also an identical spot on TLC with aniline was obtained by extracting the steam distillate with ether. The residue was filtered and crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 210°. Found, N : 15.10%; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{SO}$ requires, N : 15.05%.

Biological activity : 2-(*p*-bromophenyl)-imino-3-(*p*-bromo phenyl)-7-chloro-2:3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxaline was found to be active against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*. It also showed antifungal activity against *T. mentagrophytes* and *T. rubrum*. It showed antiameobic acitivity against *E. histolytica*.

Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh

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